

The Study of Culinary Tourism Management - A Tool for Revenue Generation and its Importance for Pune's Economic Status

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ABSTRACT

The concept of culinary tourism is taking shape and making its mark in the tourism Industry of Pune city. The venture is a part of experience industry where the memorable experiences are counted as a worth of the industry preservice. Food is an integral part of human's life and hence as long as life sustains the industry will always grow. Culinary tourism is considered as food experiences taken outside as well as inside the tourism boundaries. The city of Pune is growing in all aspects and hence the tourism is also growing which will create new opportunities for the locals to improve on their food experience and share those with others. This whole process will indeed create many avenues of creating revenue resources for the residents. This paper focuses upon the fact that culinary tourism is a very sustainable way of establishing new career opportunities in any region, which also give recognition to the traditional local cuisine. As observed in the paper Maharashtrian cuisine gets its popularity due to growth in culinary tourism of Pune region.

Keywords: Culinary tourism, Revenue generation, Food associated business

INTRODUCTION

Culinary tourism is a part of Experience Industry, which says it all that if the experience is good then the growth is directly associated with it. The fastest growth in tourism is the culinary sector. Farmers markets, taste tours, agri-entertainment, restaurants, farm shops, wineries, and boutique food retailers ...

food tourism has become an important part of holiday and business travel as well as a purpose in itself. Food tourism helps in creating entrepreneurship as well as employment opportunities. Growth in Food tourism will also help open more job or employment opportunities to the citizens of Pune. when the employment opportunities are getting increased which directly gives a boost to the revenue generation in associated sectors .When the industry will grow the quantum of work will become big hence it will require more and more services to be provided to the tourists of Pune. Pune is one of the metro cities of India and it is also one of the fast growing smart city of India, Pune is also a culture hub of Maharashtra hence it welcomes number of inbound and out bound tourists every day. As the tourism of Pune increasing the requirement of food by the tourists will also increase which automatically give a chance to culinary tourism industry to flourish in its own way and generate more resources of revenue through food Industry. The tourism of Pune region is growing every day. Food and tourism are two interdependent industries, every tourist visiting to Pune whether for leisure or business would eat his meals out during his stay. Many a times the stay of tourists is inclusive of breakfast and dinner, but they opt for lunch out. Most of the times the tourist would love to explore something new in their food that the regular meals of their daily routine. On the search of innovative and interesting meals they indirectly promote food tourism to fulfill the needs of students coming to study in Pune from other states every day new kiosks or cafes

are blooming around the college campuses and the residential zones of hostels. These outlet either serve the local popular preparations or they serve the other regional popular preparations. In both the cases it is helping to promote food tourism as well as to create new employment opportunity. These student will refer their experienced to other national, regional and international students and then the requirement of the local food increases which increases the revenue generated through these mess, dining halls, cafes and etc. When the tourism of any region increases then the ancillary and supporting businesses would also grow like Transportation, Business of souvenir shops at the tourists shops, tourists guides. The Lodging and boarding industry and many more food tourism is all about new culinary experiences. The awareness about the food tourism will help to get more and more business to specialty restaurants also to the exhibition stalls and agro tourism as the locals would travel more and more to explore new delicacies of the regional cuisines. When these ancillary business will start getting more business through the growth of agro and culinary tourism the services will establish more and contribute to the economic growth of the city. The different television shows focusing on the different cuisines and the cultures also try to educate the viewer's more about cuisines of their interest and they would give an experience on authentic food of particular cuisine to its viewer without actually visiting the destinations because food tourism is experience industry these cookery shows are definitely playing a bigger role in the growth of the food tourism. This opens a new window of employment and a section in food industry for chefs to explore their talent if they are successful then this will generate enough revenue for the media as well as food industry and can be established as a another resource of revenue generation. The linkages between food and tourism also provide a platform for local economic development. The role of food in tourism has recently received increased attention within the Pune region.

This research addresses and unfolds the potential of Food Tourism in Pune. The Consumption of food in travel is unique because it occurs in a foreign environment. Most of the times it is proven that majority percentage of the total budget is spend on food during the travel. The 2004 Restaurant & Foodservice Market Research Handbook states that 50% of restaurants' revenue was generated by

travelers. It shows that there is a symbiotic relationship between food and the tourism industry.

This study is limited to few food industry sectors and few associated businesses but that is an example which can be set to understand the positive and beneficial effects of growth of culinary tourism to the region and the financial growth of the city. Revenue generation is a basic motto of any business hence if it is not achieved then the sustainability is very difficult, so it proves that if the culinary tourism is making its mark in the pune tourism industry then there is noticeable revenue generation through this business.

Significance of the study

Food consumption can be used in the development of a destination image. In addition culinary tourism is not only appealing to tourists, but also contributes to the social, economic and environmental development of a destination. The research highlights the importance of the connection between food and tourism which cannot be ignored.

The aim of culinary tourism is to tutor and encourage food and wine fanatics while giving the vacationer a chance to explore the local area and learn about local food fashions, when the demand is the supply is also relatively high this proves that the change in demand for the food selling avenues will have a significant impact on the business and revenue generation by them which in return proves that food industry is a major part of tourism industries economic growth

Scope of the study

There is a wide scope on the angles of Indian Tourism economic growth using culinary tourism as a tool the role of Culinary Tourism in local economic development and its potential for country branding. It also presents several innovative case studies in the Culinary Tourism sector and the experience industry. Close relationship between local agriculture and tourism, clearly enhancing the environment in two different ways: Increasing the level of both food venders and tour operators taking more efforts to reach out to as many as culinary tourists to increase the demand of culinary tourism in the region of Pune.

The scope of this study is associated only with the region of pune but its sustainability can be used to apply the results on other regions. The scope is limited to few popular food sectors although there is a requirement of more and more deep research.

Definition

Culinary tourism is any tourism experience in which one learns, appreciates, and consumes branded local culinary resources.

Literature Review

Jakša Kivela and John C. Crofts (2016): the research explores that gastronomy is becoming an important attribute in the development of niche travel and destinations. The study was undertaken in which a city of destination that offers unique and diverse gastronomy is arguably. The outcomes of the study had also provided the evidence suggesting that motivation to travel for gastronomy reasons is a valid construct. Also, reveals that gastronomy plays a major role in the way tourists experience the destination and indicate that some travelers would return to the same destination to savor its unique gastronomy.

Björk, Peter and Kauppinen-Räsänen, Hannele (2016): The study had aims to explore the factors affecting traveler's food behaviour with reference to the local food market. The local food singularity represents essential research issues from various perspectives. The study had revealed three types of food-related behaviour i.e. Experiencers are committed; they perceive food as essential to destination choices. And search for the food-related information before their trip which in-turn will value the originality, newness, locality, authenticity and uniqueness in local food, which has an impact on travel satisfaction. Authentic Local food attracts travelers and it contributes to the tourist experience, indicating marketing potential for hospitality industries, tourism business and regional development.

Silkes Carol (2012) the study had explored the motivation of visitors towards farmers market and identify the potential of culinary tourist that contributes towards the economic sustainability of a local market. The study had identified that the push factors of fun and relaxation and family togetherness and the pull factors of food quality, shopping experience, and facility. It was found that pull factors of motivation play a vital role in attracting guests to a market. The research study had also exposed that quality food and a good shopping facility are the most significant factors for improving customer satisfaction. Moreover, these factors also had an impact on the cultivation of successful farmers'

market operations and contribute to culinary tourism. This can play a critical role in sustaining the economic impact of their local community and also serve as a unique niche of culinary tourism.

Everett Sally (2012): The article had examined the conversion of food production sites into spaces of touristic experience. The traditional food manufacturers are opening their doors to visitors as the popularity of food tourism increases, negotiating a balance between the operation of their business and the drive towards developing new arenas of consumption for the manufacturers who create new spaces of consumptive leisure to accommodate touristic interests, the constructive agency of tourist expectations and insights into how producers alter patterns of traditional production to facilitate growing consumptive demands.

Hong, Jeou-Shyan, Liu Chih-Hsing, Chou Hsin-Yu and Tsai Chang-Yen (2012): Had explored the factors of brand equity and the role of destination knowledge for travel intentions in culinary tourism from the viewpoint of foreign tourists travelling to various destinations, which promoters four elements for brand equity i.e. loyalty, image, perceived quality and awareness for culinary travel intentions. The research had developed and empirically tested a model of the relationship, the results indicate that there is a straight and strong association between brand equity and travel intentions in culinary tourism. Moreover, the study had recognized the moderating role of destination awareness, which positively moderates the effect of brand loyalty and perceived quality on travel intentions.

Gary Paul Green & Michael L. Dougherty (2009): The study had examined culinary tourism through a case study the retail establishments relied heavily on local produce, largely due to a commitment to help local producers. Farmers frequently combined marketing fresh food to local retail establishments with sales to wholesalers. The most frequently cited concerns with producing for local establishments involved in culinary tourism were low prices and challenging logistics.

Stephen L. J. Smith, Honggen Xiao (2008): The centrality of local ingredients and culinary resources to the culinary tourism experience means that an understanding of the issues and structures associated with accessing those resources can contribute to a

deeper understanding of culinary tourism as a product and its linkages to other sectors of the economy. Supply chain theory is introduced and its relevance to culinary tourism discussed. A preliminary description of the supply chains for three culinary tourism products—farmers' markets, festivals, and restaurants—are identified on the basis of semi structured discussions with representatives from the three product sectors.

Mason Robb and O'Mahony Barry (2007): The basic purpose of the research was twofold i.e. to identify important factors in the development of food and wine trails within the context of culinary tourism and to propose methods by which trail businesses that can additionally build on the tourism potential of food and wine. The trail development factors identified are the trail as a tourist product, the relevance of alternative food networks, and the identity of the culinary tourist. The research suggests that a difficulty facing trail developers is the problem of incorporating a tourism product into what is essentially a cooperative marketing mechanism and the ways in which trail businesses can construct narratives in order to improve 'meaningful experiences' for contemporary culinary tourists

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To enumerate the various career opportunities created due to food tourism and their revenue generation capabilities.
2. To understand the benefits of food tourism to the economic growth of Pune.
3. To analyze the factors influencing the financial and economic status of food tourism in Pune city.

Research Methodology

The various strategies adopted by the food tourists in the Pune region have been compiled by carrying out a rigorous survey across Pune Region. These strategies were floated in the form of questionnaires and the feedback was collected on the basis of this survey. This questionnaire was circulated amongst mixed samples from all work areas of the region. The sample types included managerial and other staff members which will cover almost all group of employees working in the service and corporate sectors. This survey was specifically carried out to evaluate the mind-set of the food tourist and the food vendors to understand whether the concept of food tourism is also a better option to create various career and

employment opportunity for the locals as well as the foodies of the region.

Type of Research: A descriptive research was used to study the various employment and career avenues opened and which can sustain if the food tourism of the region flourishes.

Methods of Data Collection

Primary Data - was collected from the locals working in various service and corporate sectors around Pune city. Primary data was collected through survey in the following ways:

1. **Personal Interviews:** The answer was sought to a set of pre-conceived questions through personal interviews and the data was collected in a structured way.
2. **Questionnaires:** Considering the Reviews, and the additional inputs, one schedule was prepared it was a questionnaire designed for the inbound and out bound travelers of the Pune as well as foodies of the Pune residing in the region and exploring food of all corners

Secondary Data – was collected from published / unpublished literature on the importance of Food Tourism and its impact in creating revenue resources for the food industry. latest references available from the journals, newspapers, research publications and magazines, past records and training reports of the food establishments, and other relevant sources like internet.

Questionnaire – Design and implementation: The questionnaire design was done with the aid of experts in statistical techniques and taking into account the measurement needs & objectives of the study. The questionnaire was administered to the sample population and sample size.

Sampling Techniques: For this study different employee from various star hotels in and around Pune city who are working at a Managerial level was taken into consideration. This involves a total of 100 samples from the respondents.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

The data collected was analyzed using basic and advanced analytical tools. This also includes the detailed analysis of the data which was conducted with the purpose of attaining the set objectives of the

research. Mentioned below is the analysis which be presented graphically and in tabulated form for better interpretation. The Interpretation of the collected data was done by drawing inferences from the collected facts after the analysis of the study.

Food tourism is a major source of generating employment as well as revenue for the sector of tourism Industry. According to the survey which was conducted among the locals of Pune region and inbound, out bound tourists the employment and career opportunities offered by food tourism are many

and sustainable. The respondents were from different age group and profession so that the feedback can be collected from all classes of people and possibly well-travelled people.

The below frequency table will illustrate the feedbacks which can sum to the results whether the employment and career opportunities generated by food tourism are sustainable and do they have a progressive future.

1. Identification of sectors which can generating maximum employment opportunities.

a. Food Joints

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
8 (Most Important)	69	27.17%
7	34	13.39%
6	27	10.63%
5	13	5.12%
4	17	6.69%
3	13	5.12%
2	21	8.27%
1 (Least Important)	60	23.62%

Importance of Food Joints in Employment Generation

Observations:

It was found that Food joints were rated as most important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 85 respondents but on the other hand it was rated as least important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 74 respondents but in all 50% respondents have rated Food joints as effective tool to generate employment.

Interpretation:

The statistical interpretation will prove that more than 50% respondents find food joint as effective tool to generate employment which in many aspects promote Culinary Tourism.

a. Fairs and Festivals

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
8 (Most Important)	25	9.84%
7	48	18.90%
6	34	13.39%
5	27	10.63%
4	29	11.42%
3	27	10.63%
2	47	18.50%
1 (Least Important)	17	6.69%

Importance of Fairs & Festivals in Employment Generation**Observations:**

It was found that fairs and festivals were rated as most important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 25 respondents but on the other hand it was rated as least important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 17 respondents but in all 42% respondents have rated Fairs and festivals as effective tool to generate employment.

Interpretation:

The statistical interpretation will prove that more than 40% respondents find fairs and festivals as effective tool to generate employment and on the contrary more than 37% respondents find fairs and festival as least effective tool for generating employment which in many aspects promote Culinary Tourism. The fairs and festival always try and show case any of the regional food specialty to its visitors so it is considered as tool for promoting Culinary Tourism.

b. Television Shows

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
8 (Most Important)	23	9.06%
7	22	8.66%
6	41	16.14%
5	39	15.35%
4	20	7.87%
3	52	20.47%
2	27	10.63%
1 (Least Important)	30	11.81%

Importance of Television Shows in Employment Generation

Observations:

It was found that television shows were rated as most important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 23 respondents but on the other hand it was rated as least important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 30 respondents but in all 26% respondents have rated television as effective tool to generate employment

Interpretation:

The statistical interpretation will prove that more than 25 % respondents find television shows as effective tool to generate employment and on the contrary more than 42% respondents find Television shows as least effective tool for generating employment which in many aspects promote Culinary Tourism. The television shows which are based on food and discovery of different cuisines on the channels like travel and living, discovery, fox life are basically an virtual tool to make the people knowledgeable about different cuisines its specialties only on one click without travelling physically but as it enlightens the foodies about new food and cuisines it is considered as a tool to promote Culinary Tourism and advertising marketing tool for promoting Culinary Tourism but looking at the statistical responses it may not be very effective tool to generate employment under the segment of Culinary Tourism.

c. Cookery Classes

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
8 (Most Important)	8	3.15%
7	21	8.27%
6	20	7.87%
5	44	17.32%
4	74	29.13%
3	29	11.42%
2	34	13.39%
1 (Least Important)	24	9.45%

Importance of Cookery Classes in Employment Generation

Observations:

It was found that cookery classes were rated as most important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 8 respondents but on the other hand it was rated as least important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 24 respondents but in all 19% respondents have rated television as effective tool to generate employment.

Interpretation:

The statistical interpretation will prove that more than 19 % respondents find cookery classes as effective tool to generate employment and on the contrary more than 35% respondents find cookery classes as least effective tool for generating employment, which in many aspects promote Culinary Tourism. The cookery classes which are based on the need of enthusiastic people who are eager to learn more varieties of food under different cuisines to make the people knowledgeable about different cuisines its specialties these cookery classes by professionals are helpful without travelling physically but as it enlightens the foodies about new food and cuisines it is considered as a tool to promote Culinary Tourism and advertising marketing tool for promoting Culinary Tourism but looking at the statistical responses it may not be very effective tool to generate employment under the segment of Culinary Tourism.

d. Food Walks

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
8 (Most Important)	13	5.12%
7	17	6.69%
6	29	11.42%
5	59	23.23%
4	47	18.50%
3	34	13.39%
2	26	10.24%
1 (Least Important)	29	11.42%

Importance of Food Walks in Employment Generation

Observations:

It was found that Food walks were rated as most important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 16 respondents but on the other hand it was rated as least important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 36 respondents but in all 23.3% respondents have rated food walks as effective tool to generate employment.

Interpretation:

The statistical interpretation will prove that more than 23.3% respondents find food walks as effective tool to generate employment and on the contrary more than 35% respondents find food walks as least effective tool for generating employment which in many aspects promote Culinary Tourism. The food walks is a concept where the travelers can explore various regional specialties during the local side signing or he can be guided by the food tour guide to various local specialty serving outlets which can be a shop, restaurant, canteen or a home cooking.

e. Agricultural Tourism

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
8 (Most Important)	20	7.87%
7	24	9.45%
6	52	20.47%
5	24	9.45%
4	28	11.02%
3	52	20.47%
2	27	10.63%
1 (Least Important)	27	10.63%

Importance of Agricultural Tourism in Employment Generation**Observations:**

It was found that television shows were rated as most important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 25 respondents but on the other hand it was rated as least important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 33 respondents but in all 26% respondents have rated television as effective tool to generate employment.

Interpretation:

The statistical interpretation will prove that more than 36% respondents find Agricultural tourism as effective tool to generate employment and on the contrary more than 41% respondents find Agricultural tourism as least effective tool for generating employment which in many aspects promote Culinary Tourism. The agro tourism and Culinary Tourism go hand in hand as both are interdependent on each other. The concept of Agricultural tourism is to make the travelers aware about the village life, and to allow them to explore the fresh robust

cooking culture of the agro produces. Many at times it becomes a side business for the farmers to earn some additional income.

f. Visit to Farms for Rural Food

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
8 (Most Important)	18	7.09%
7	55	21.65%
6	27	10.63%
5	20	7.87%
4	25	9.84%
3	21	8.27%
2	53	20.87%
1 (Least Important)	35	13.78%

Importance of Visit to Farms in Employment Generation

Observations:

It was found that visit to farms were rated as most important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 18 respondents but on the other hand it was rated as least important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 35 respondents but in all 39 % respondents have rated television as effective tool to generate employment.

Interpretation:

The statistical interpretation will prove that more than 39% respondents find television shows as effective tool to generate employment and on the contrary more than 42% respondents find visit to farms as least effective tool for generating employment which in many aspects promote Culinary Tourism. Visit to farms is a part of agro tourism and more effective for cultural tourism but as discussed in the literature review chapter food is an inseparable part of cultural tourism.

g. Specialty Restaurant

Particular	frequency	Percentage
8 (Most Important)	96	30.71%
7	41	12.99%
6	29	9.45%
5	34	11.02%
4	17	5.51%
3	32	10.24%
2	23	7.48%
1 (Least Important)	39	12.60%

Importance of Specialty Restaurant in Employment Generation**Observations:**

It was found that Specialty restaurants were rated as most important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 96 respondents but on the other hand it was rated as least important tool for generating employment under Culinary Tourism by 39 respondents but in all 52 % respondents have rated specialty restaurants as effective tool to generate employment

Interpretation:

The statistical interpretation will prove that more than 52 % respondents find television shows as effective tool to generate employment and on the contrary more than 31% respondents find Specialty restaurants as least effective tool for generating employment which in many aspects promote Culinary Tourism. Specialty restaurants directly promote Culinary Tourism so they are the most effective tool to generate employment under Culinary Tourism and the same is the opinion of the respondents

2. Culinary Tourism contributes towards the financial growth of Tourism Industry

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
1 (Least contribution)	2	0.79%
2	6	1.97%
3	76	24.41%
4	131	42.13%
5 (highest contribution)	96	30.71%

Contribution of Culinary Tourism in Growth of Tourism Industry

Observation:

As discussed in the literature review Culinary Tourism is a part of Experience economy hence the financial growth of Culinary Tourism industry is very much related on the food experiences. Culinary Tourism defiantly contributes towards the financial growth of tourism industry. According to the responses received total 96 respondents feel that Culinary Tourism has highest contribution towards the financial growth of tourism industry and total 2 respondents feel that Culinary Tourism has least contribution towards the financial growth of tourism industry

Interpretation:

Total distribution of responses from least distribution to highest distribution was spread over the 1 to 5 numbers, where number 1 was representing least contribution and number 5 was representing highest contribution .After studying the total responses received the researcher has found out more than 72% respondents feel that Culinary Tourism has highest contribution towards the financial growth of tourism industry, on the contrary total 3% respondents feel that it has least contribution towards the financial growth of tourism industry. Whereas more than 24% respondents feel neutral as they had rated number 3

which means they feel it does contribute towards the financial growth of tourism industry but it is neither highest nor least.

3. Supporting Businesses for Culinary Tourism

The below listed are most important supporting businesses for Culinary Tourism

- Event Management
- Catering
- Transportation
- Cultural and Art Appreciation
- Cloth, Jewelry, Souvenir Shops
- Guide and Tour operators
- All the above business

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Event Management	158	50.79%
Catering	179	57.48%
Transportation	206	66.14%
Cultural and Art Appreciation	97	31.10%
Cloth, Jewelry, Souvenir Shop	50	16.14%
Guide and Tour Operators	98	31.50%
All of the Above	98	31.50%

Importance of Supporting Businesses for Culinary Tourism

Observations:

Around 66% which means 206 respondents feel that Transportation is the most effective supporting business for Culinary Tourism as an employment generating sector. Whereas 179 which is around 57.48% respondents support Catering as second most important business in the list of Supporting business for the Culinary Tourism. 98 respondents which is 31% feel that Catering, Transportation, Cultural and Art Appreciation, Cloth, Jewelry, Souvenir Shop, Guide and tour Operators are all important business

Interpretation:

Most of the listed Business are directly or Indirectly linked with the Culinary Tourism, but the researcher would like to identify which of these are most effective in generating employment as it is linked with Culinary Tourism so if Culinary Tourism will flourish in the region as a business then these businesses will also have a positive impact in generating more.

Observations and Findings

The first and foremost observation is that the concept of food tourism is well established in the region of Pune but still there is lot of scope for the tourists to aware themselves about the concept to become food tourists. The awareness about food tourism is still lacking. Pune is also known as oxford of the western India hence it welcomes lot of international as well as national students from all corners and food is one of their basic need for daily routine. While doing this directly and indirectly Pune opens lot of different opportunities in the food sector and service sector for employment and career. At the same time it will open lot of opportunities for the entrepreneurship growth of the food tourism industry. The observations are listed as follows

1. All sectors of service and corporate industry people, all age group people believe that, food tourism creates many opportunities for the employment and careers
2. As a result of food tourism different other business also get more opportunities of revenue generation, in effect the business grows and creates more job or employment for the locals.
3. Food Stalls, Mess, Restaurants, Specialty outlets, Kiosks, Stalls at exhibitions, Food tour operators, local food vendors and many more business are indirectly growing as the tourism of the region develops and increases. When they are growing they are contributing to the economic growth of their own business sector as well as the growth of Pune city
4. Many a times the occasional food business also give noticeable revenue that the regular set ups like food stall of specialties during the fairs and jattras, food supply during wedding and festive seasons etc.
5. Researcher also observed that there is lot of scope for the food in the Agro tourism and it can get lot of revenue to the rural areas around the Pune and it will get popularity to the local Maharashtrian cuisine as well
6. It was observed that few things do influence the sustainability of food tourism of the Pune region. These include:
 - Popularity of Local food
 - Good revenue Margins of the supporting business
 - Festive Specialties served or sold by the vendors at all possible places will increase the business and the revenue directly
 - To explore new varieties lot of tourists make conscious efforts provided they get enough avenues to explore
 - To break the monotony of daily Routine many locals and foodies explore different food which helps in food tourism growth and revenue generation

Findings

According to the graphical representation shown in the above graphs about the talent retention management for hotel industry, below mentioned were some of the interpretations that were drawn from the analysis:

1. Majority of the respondents were agreeing upon the provision of a better exposure to the tourists and more advertisement will help the food tourism to grow in the region of Pune

2. The provision of Food, at various tourists destinations with lot of more and more varieties will improve the status of the Maharashtra cuisines popularity
 3. The food vendors to undertake more aggressive marketing strategies to increase their food business which indirectly will bring lot of revenue to the industry the tourism Industry should conduct several in-house activities for the tourists to offered them every time new experience
 4. Hotels should offer new varieties to their food tourists to explore new, new cuisine of the regions will bring curiosity in the tourists' mind which will make them visit again and again and helps in repetitive business, this will help in sustaining the industry.
 5. The key findings of the research says that the sustainability of the food tourism industry and the popularity of local food will bring more tourists to the region which indeed will get more revenues and the growth will open lot of many more employment opportunities
 6. Many side and supporting business to the tourism industry are growing because the food tourism industry is growing
- The hospitality industry of the city of Pune will welcome many tourists who explore local cuisine and culture in all possible ways during their stay .this will lead an increase in demand of food supplied by restaurants, shops, kiosks, food walks, specialty restaurants, etc.
 - When there will be more demand for the food supply the employment will be more as the industry is a labor extensive industry. This gives a birth to new business avenues of fairs, festivals, event management, packaged food, more convenience products which can be carried away etc.
 - The research also supports the cause that the growing culinary tourism of the region will help to sustain the overall economic growth of the tourism industry of the Pune region and when the economy develops it brings many good changes to the total growth of the city and life style of people
 - Pune have recognized their potentials concerning Culinary Tourism and have put concrete efforts to promoting their images as culinary Tourism destinations.
 - However, the road to success requires joint contribution of business owners, marketers, policy makers, etc.

Recommendations and Suggestions

1. The local food vendors to take special efforts for the promotion of Maharashtra food.
2. The vendor should sponsor the major festivals and events in the region either by sponsoring the meals or by giving hampers of their specialties for the visitors.
3. The local food vendors should start small food tour around the city in alliance with the tour operators.
4. The food vendors to offer special discount for the regular tour operators as a motivation to get more and more tourists to their places.
5. Sustenance is a key piece of all societies, the linkages amongst Food and tourism likewise give a stage to nearby monetary improvement, which can be reinforced by the utilization of sustenance encounters for marketing and advertising goals.

Conclusion

- The research also proves one major factor of increasing employment opportunities and career as well as entrepreneur opportunities due to increase in the culinary tourism of the region.

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